

PROVIDING THE INTEGRATION OF PEDAGOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN MODERN EDUCATION

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Annotation

In this article, the integration of pedagogical and information technologies is a complex integrative process that includes the analysis and planning of the problem that covers all aspects of knowledge acquisition, the evaluation of the solution to the problem, the methods of organizing activities, and the integration of pedagogical and information technologies in improving the methodological preparation of future teachers, and through this, a potential pedagogical content of upbringing, legal bases and existing conditions were studied.

Key words: pedagogue, integration, information, information technology, method, pedagogical skill, legal basis.

INTRODUCTION Today, the introduction of "new state education standards" once again imposes demands on the teacher that significantly change professional activity and fill it with new content. Because these standards are based on a competent-active approach, they differ from their predecessors in that they are oriented not to the formation of knowledge, skills and qualifications, but to the formation of a person capable of continuous education, development of needs and abilities. Therefore, the increase in professional responsibilities of teachers and changes in their role in society require them to have the qualities of quick adaptation to rapid changes in the educational process, extreme activity, readiness for continuous self-development and independent learning, knowledge of modern approaches and technologies of teaching, and the ability to use them effectively [1]. Therefore, it is one of the urgent tasks to ensure the integration of competence based on pedagogical and information technologies in improving the methodical training of future teachers. The use of an integrative approach in the development of methodical training of future teachers and the use of information processing technology in it is a unique innovative approach in the field of pedagogy, with the help of which it has a positive effect on the research process. quality change and higher efficiency are achieved.

Analysis of literature on the topic.

Setting the issues of ensuring the integration of pedagogical opportunities and information technologies in modern education M.Tillashakhova, O.Abdquddusov, D.I.Yusupova, I.Ya.Rakhmonov, B.Boltaev, O. It was researched by such scientists as Yu. Kovalenko, N. Kayumova, U. N. Taylakov, R. G'. Safarova, and B. Kh. Rakhimov. American researchers K. Zeichner (Zeichner) and S. Ray (Wray) interpreted the information and theories related to the problem to ensure the integration of information technologies.

According to world pedagogues-psychologists, a possible way to manage knowledge is to organize the mastering process as a mastering process of a given task. A better developed system in this area is the educational system based on P.Ya. Galperin's theory of formation of mental actions by stages. According to this theory, processes of internalization of actions occur in the ontogenetic development of a person, that is, processes of gradual transformation of external actions into internal mental actions. At first, students work with external material movement, "only then the integration of the movement occurs, that is, its transformation into an internal movement, now a movement that becomes an event in the child's mind", writes A.N. Leontev [2].

Analysis and results.

During the application of information technologies in education, special software tools are used along with technical tools. "A software tool focused on the educational process is a software tool reflected in the study of a field of science, which provides the technology for studying this field of science and the conditions for the implementation of various educational activities related to it. Software tools that provide such functionality for various types of educational processes are called pedagogical software tools. Currently, there are various types and groups of pedagogical software tools. Pedagogical software tools, depending on their methodological function, include: computer textbooks (lessons); tutoring programs; control programs (test shells); information-guide (encyclopedia) programs; simulation programs; modeling programs; presentation programs (slides, video films); educational programs; programs aimed at meaningful spending of free time (computer games: fun games, strategic games, controlled games, logical games, sports games, etc.)"[3].

Based on the goal of the methodological system of training future teachers in the integration of pedagogical and information technologies, "one of the main directions of quality pedagogue training is the organization of direct pedagogical activities in the classes of laboratories of specialized sciences: developing lesson plans, technological maps of the lesson, giving lessons to fellow students, analyzing students preparation for pedagogical activity is preparation" [4]. Therefore, it is necessary to improve the methodical training system in order to educate a competitive staff and the personality of a modern pedagogue.

He should be ready to carry out pedagogical activities in educational institutions, "organize teaching of informatics and information technologies using educational programs and textbooks of different levels, know the methodical system and its constituent elements. In order to develop the methodical system of the teacher in the integration of pedagogical and information technologies, if the methodical system and its constituent elements are formed by the teacher in the mind of the students during each lesson of the specialty, a reflexive approach to the creation of the methodical system is formed in the student" [5].

It is also appropriate to take into account the main directions of the government's state policy in the field of informatization when improving the methodological training of future teachers based on the integration of pedagogical and information technologies. According to him:

- implementation of everyone's constitutional rights to freely receive and disseminate information, ensuring free use of information resources;
- creation of a single information space of the Republic of Uzbekistan based on information systems of state bodies, network and regional information systems, as well as information systems of legal entities and individuals;

creating conditions for free use of international information networks and the Internet world information network;

formation of state information resources, creation and development of information systems, ensuring their compatibility and interaction;

organization of production of modern means of information technologies;

to support the formation of the market of information resources, services and information technologies;

stimulating the development of software products production;

supporting and encouraging entrepreneurship, creating favorable conditions for attracting investments;

consists of personnel training and improvement of their qualifications, stimulation of scientific research [6]. Based on these priorities, the future teacher will need to develop his knowledge of information technologies and be able to integrate them with the knowledge and skills of his specialty. A pedagogue who is able to accomplish this integrative task can show high results in his pedagogical activity. The problem of developing innovative methodical activities in education includes many independent issues and determines a number of conceptual rules. These require the development of concrete technological issues of innovative methodical training of the pedagogue.

These include:

- creation of integrative and differential educational technologies;

- formation of a system of ideas about new educational processes;

- pedagogical tools ensuring the relevance of integrated components of education;

- creation of an innovative environment in a higher education institution;

- technological and methodical factors affecting the determination of individual characteristics in the implementation of new methodical activities. The specified conceptual rules require that the process of developing innovative methodical activity requires a dialectical relationship between the teacher and the subject of education. Innovative educational methodical activity is an integral concept, the components of which are cultural knowledge, professional culture, creative culture, culture of intellectual property rights, culture of perception of innovation, culture of management, physical culture.

Conclusions and suggestions.

In conclusion, it can be said that in our country, the integration of pedagogical activities with information technologies is a necessary requirement in the professional activity of today's pedagogue. Because it is impossible to imagine today's education without information technologies, the teacher's deep knowledge of them becomes an important vital requirement. However, it remains one of the urgent tasks to establish how and in what form and with what considerations their integration should take place, scientific research and development of important scientific conclusions. In the preparation of future teachers for integrated methodological activities, it is necessary to achieve harmony in the formation of their general cultural potential, specialized knowledge and personal qualities. Therefore, there is a need for integration of all knowledge-related subjects provided in the curriculum. Therefore, it is based on the strengthening of interdisciplinary relations in the teaching of integrated methodical activities. It is important to use new pedagogical technologies and interactive teaching methods in order to develop students' independent thinking and creative abilities in mastering subjects. Therefore, person-centered learning can work well under the influence of

collaborative pedagogy, small group work methods. The wide introduction of modern information communications will give a good result in increasing the efficiency of educational technologies.

It will be possible to make the following proposals for ensuring the integration of pedagogical opportunities and information technologies in modern education:

- creation of integrative and differential educational technologies;
 - formation of a system of ideas about new educational processes;
 - Pedagogical tools ensuring the relevance of integrated components of education;
 - creation of an innovative environment in a higher education institution;
- technological and methodical factors affecting the determination of individual characteristics in the implementation of new methodical activities. The specified conceptual rules require that the process of developing innovative methodical activity requires a dialectical relationship between the teacher and the subject of education.

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